

Halogenated Metabolites from Marine Animals and Plants

R. H. THOMSON

Department of Chemistry, University of Aberdeen,
Meston Walk, Old Aberdeen. AB9 2UE Scotland

A large number of halogenated compounds have been isolated from marine animals and plants. Bromo derivatives occur most frequently, and iodo compounds are comparatively rare. The principal types are halogenated phenols, terpenes, and simple aliphatic compounds, with smaller groups of indoles, pyrroles and acetylenes.

IN a review of naturally occurring halogenated organic compounds covering the literature to the end of 1972 Siuda and DeBernardis¹ surveyed over 200 compounds, of which some 50, nearly all containing bromine, were obtained from marine sources. Since then research² on marine natural products has continued apace, halogenated metabolites have become commonplace, and the presence of bromine and chlorine is now as unremarkable as that of oxygen or nitrogen. Nevertheless the number (approaching 300) and variety of marine metabolites containing halogen is probably not appreciated by those outside the field, and this applies particularly in India where, despite a long sustained interest in natural products—and a long coastline—the chemistry of marine organisms is still neglected. Apart from their chemical interest, many of the compounds discussed in the following pages show antibiotic activity. As yet none of these are of commercial significance but they provide some stimulus for the continuing search for “drugs from the sea”.³

In view of the abundance of halide ion in the sea ($\text{Cl}^- \sim 19 \text{ g./l.}$, $\text{Br}^- \sim 65 \text{ mg./l.}$, I^- (and IO_3^-) $\sim 60 \mu\text{g./l.}$) it is not surprising to find that many marine organisms make use of it, the predominance of bromo compounds probably reflecting the easier oxidation of bromide (relative to chloride) to the actual halogenating species. Organic iodo compounds are comparatively rare despite the fact that certain seaweeds were at one time a commercial source of iodine, and it is possible to extract free iodine directly from some algae. In part, however, the apparent rarity may be attributable to the weakness of the carbon-iodine bond which does not always survive extraction procedures.

In a very early paper entitled “Beitrag zur Chemie einiger Seethiere” Drechsel⁴ isolated an iodoaminoacid by hydrolysis of the horny skeleton of *Gorgonia cavolinii*. This was shown subsequently to be 3,5-diodotyrosine, and a few years later 3,5-dibromotyrosine (1) was obtained⁵ similarly from the protein of another coral. The dibromoaminoacid is the probable precursor of a group of brominated compounds found in recent years in *Verongia* and *Ianthella* sponges which include *inter alia* the amidodienone (2)⁶, the rearranged amide (3)⁷,

benzene-1,2-diol which has been isolated as the (+)-form from *Verongia*⁸ and the (-)-form from *Ianthella*⁹, and aeroplysinin-2 (5) found¹⁰ as the (+)-form in *Verongia* and as the racemate in *Ianthella*. Aerothionin (6; $n=4$) and homoaerothionin (6; $n=5$)

are more complex members of the group¹¹. Racemic aeroplysinin-1 (4) has been synthesised¹² from the phenol (7) by oxidation with lead tetra-acetate in acetic acid to the acetoxydienone (8; $\text{R}=\text{Ac}$) which was converted to the alcohol (8; $\text{R}=\text{H}$), and then reduced with sodium borohydride. In an approach to the

synthesis¹³ of (\pm)-aerotherionin (6; $n=4$), the bis-phenolic oxime (9) was oxidatively cyclised with manganese(III) tris-acetylacetonate to the bis-spirodienone (10) which was reduced with sodium borohydride. However the product isolated was the *cis-cis* isomer of (6; $n=4$) whereas the natural product is the *trans-trans* form¹⁴.

Probably the best known halogenated compound from marine life is the ancient purple dye, Tyrian Purple (11)¹⁵, obtained from Muricidae and Thaisidae molluscs. The structure of the pigment, which is an artefact, was established¹⁶ in the early 1900s, and sixty years elapsed before the colourless precursors, (12) and related indoxyls, were recognised¹⁷.

Tyrian Purple remained unique until analogous indigoids were discovered¹⁸ very recently in the acorn worm *Ptychodera flava*. This animal is normally yellow but a collection of unusual green specimens was found to contain the blue pigments (13) and (14), as well as (11). The indole (15) was also isolated. Normal, yellow, *P. flava* contain trace amounts of 3-chloro-

3-bromo- and 6-bromo-3-chloroindole¹⁹ which are responsible for their "iodoform-like" odour. Other halogenated 'marine indoles' are the sponge metabolites (16; $R=H$ and Me)²⁰ and (17)²¹ but the enormous range of indole alkaloids in terrestrial plants has no counterpart in the sea, and indeed with a few exceptions, alkaloids are absent. The betaine (17) is a bromo derivative of hypaphorine found in higher plants (Leguminosae).

Brominated pyrroles have been isolated from sponges. The monobromo derivative (18) was found²² in an unidentified *Agelas* sp., while *Agelas oroides*²³ contain the simple dibromo compounds (18a; $R=CO_2H$,²³ $CONH_2$,²³ and CN ²³) as well as

oroidin (19)²⁴ which is closely related to dibromophakellin (20)²⁵ from the sponge *Phakellia flabellata*. Little chemical work has been done on marine bacteria but some are brominating species. The pentabromo metabolite (21) is elaborated by *Pseudomonas bromotillis*²⁶, while the same compound together with tetrabromopyrrole and the hexabromopyrrole (22) (79% bromine) are produced by an unidentified *Chromobacter* sp²⁷.

Numerous brominated phenols have been found in marine animals and plants some of which have already been mentioned. 2,4-Dibromo- and 2,4,6-tribromophenol occur in the tubeworm *Phoronopsis viridis*,²⁸ and the former also in the acorn worm *Balanoglossus biminiensis*²⁹, and the latter in *P. flava laysanica*.³⁰ *P. flava* also produces³⁰ tri- and tetrabromohydroquinone, the polybromo diaryl ethers (23; $R=H$ and

Br) and the unique octabromo-bis-ether (24) which are also substituted hydroquinones. The diaryl ethers (25) and (26) have been obtained from the sponge *Dysidea herbacea*,³¹ while polyaryl ethers, known as phloro-

tannins,^{31a} occur in many of the larger brown algae. These compounds are polymers based on phloroglucinol, and are occasionally halogenated as in chlorodiphlorethol (27) from *Laminaria ochroleuca*.

Another source of interesting bromophenols is the polychaete worm *Thelepus setosus*³² which produces the related compounds (28; R=CH₂OH and CHO), and (29)-(31). The dienone, thelepin (31), can be reduced to thelephenol (30) with sodium borohydride,

and presumably (31) is formed *in vivo* by the reverse oxidation. Thelepin is similar in structure to griseofulvin from *Penicillium griseofulvum* and shows comparable antifungal activity.

Numerous simple bromophenols occur in red algae³³, and to a lesser extent in brown algae. A few are of type (28) where R=CH₂OH, CHO, CH₂CO₂H or CH₂COCO₂H, the majority being related catechols containing one to three atoms of bromine, e.g. (32) and (33). *Rhodomela lartix*, which contains³⁴ (32) and the corresponding benzyl alcohol methyl ether, was actually used in Japan as a source of bromine during the second world war³⁵. *Polystiphonia urceolata*³⁶ contains the bibenzyl derivative (34) as well as compounds of type (28) and (32), while *Rytiphlea tinctoria*³⁷ produces dibromophloroglucinol, 5,6-dibromo-3,4-dihydroxybenzyl alcohol, and the phenol (35). Simple bromophenols have also been found in

the blue-green alga *Calothrix brevisstima*³⁸, while the green calcareous alga, *Cymopolia barbata*³⁹, is the source of a group of prenylated bromohydroquinones including (36), (37), and the chromene (38).

From inspection of the foregoing formulae it is evident that aromatic halogenation is an electrophilic process which requires the equivalent of X⁺ for substitution. It is equally obvious that the source of X⁺ must be X⁻ available in abundance in the marine environment. It has been shown^{40a} that cultures of the alga *Nereocystis luetkeana* incorporate iodine from ¹³¹I⁻ into iodotyrosines, and a partially purified bromoperoxidase enzyme has been isolated^{40b} from *Cystoclonium purpureum* which catalysed the bromination of catechuic aldehyde in the presence of sodium bromide and hydrogen peroxide. Although the precise form of the electrophilic halogenating species is not known it is suggested⁴¹ that it may take the form of a hypohalite ligand (OBr, etc.) attached to the iron atom of a heme peroxidase. Hypohalites can halogenate phenols although their ability to halogenate and effect the cyclisation of acyclic terpenes has not been demonstrated *in vitro*. However this has been achieved with N-bromosuccinimide⁴², an analogous source of positive bromine and it is generally accepted⁴³ that the numerous halogenated terpenes found in algae (see below) are formed *in vivo* by way of bromonium ion intermediates. Cyclocymopol (37), a meroterpenoid, contains both aliphatic and aromatic bromine; a likely precursor is geranylhydroquinone which undergoes electrophilic attack by "enzyme-bound Br⁺" both on the benzene ring and on the terminal double bond to form the bromonium ion (39), followed by cyclisation as indicated.

The halogenated terpenes are a large group, all of which are algal products, predominantly from the Rhodophyta. It is particularly interesting that a number of these compounds which have been isolated from the digestive glands of sea hares (*Aplysia*) derive from their algal diet and are not the products of molluscan metabolism⁴⁴. *Plocamium* spp. are a good source of halogenated monoterpenes, although they occur elsewhere. These compounds possess up to six halogen atoms, many containing both chlorine and bromine [see (41),⁴⁵ (42),^{44a,46} (43)⁴⁷ and (44)⁴⁸]. While the high halogen content is obviously an advantage for the structure determination of crystalline compounds by X-ray analysis, this is not possible for liquids and it is frequently difficult to define the relative position of halogen atoms and distinguish between isomers by spectroscopic methods. Moreover these compounds are not particularly stable and the absence of molecular ions from their mass spectra is the rule rather than the exception. Sesquiterpenes are found in algae and gorgonians but so far halogenated derivatives

seem to be confined to the *Laurencia* genus, of red algae. These plants elaborate at least a dozen sesquiterpene carbon skeletons and a host of metabolites represented here by caespitol (45),⁴⁹ prepacifenol (46),⁵⁰ perforatone (47),⁵¹ and aplysin (48)⁵². Very few halogenated diterpenes have been isolated; they include iriediol (49) (from *Laurencia*⁵³) and bromosphaerol (50) (from *Sphaerococcus*⁵⁴) but higher

terpenes containing halogen are not known. Although some remarkable marine carotenoids have been discovered,⁵⁵ so far they are all halogen-free.

Some progress has been made in the synthesis of brominated sesquiterpenes using a biomimetic approach.^{43a} Brominative cyclisation is the key step demanding a careful choice of conditions and source of positive bromine. Thus α -(52) and β -(53)-snyderol were obtained⁵⁶ directly from nerolidol (51) in one step using 2,4,4,6-tetrabromocyclohexa-2,5-dienone as the source of Br⁺, but the yield of each was only ca. 2%. A similar reaction with methyl *trans*-*trans*-farnesate (54) was effected with NBS and copper(II) acetate

to give (55) as the only cyclic product (12%) from which β -snyderol was obtained in three further steps.⁵⁷ A better result was obtained when geranylacetone (56) was treated with bromine and silver fluoroborate in

nitromethane to give (57) in 20% yield. This was then rearranged to the ketone (58) with acid, extended to the snyderol isomer (59) by reaction with vinyl magnesium bromide and then cyclised in the presence of *p*-toluene-sulphonic acid to 10-bromo- α -chamigrene (60).⁵⁸ Subsequently (60) was isolated from *Laurencia pacifica*.⁵⁹

Perhaps the most intriguing halogenated marine metabolites are the very simple compounds (C₁-C₂) present in the Bonnemaisoniaceae family of red algae. These are mostly volatile compounds which have been identified by GC-MS. The investigations^{60,61} on *Asparagopsis taxiformis* have revealed an impressive array of about 80 polyhalo compounds, a selection of which is listed below. The total collection includes several haloforms, eleven

haloacetones (and acetone itself), twenty polyhaloisopropanols, a number of halo-propenes and -acroleins, sixteen halogenated butenones and butenols, and a group of dihaloacetamides. Analogous halogenated acetic and acrylic acids have been isolated (as ethyl esters) from *A. armata*.⁶¹ Many of these are very reactive compounds and about twenty contain iodine, some of which decompose, liberating free iodine, on exposure to light and air. A few compounds, like CHClBrI, could be optically active. Surprisingly, *A. taxiformis* is an edible seaweed which is highly esteemed in Hawaii and eaten uncooked, although many of its constituents appear to be toxic and possibly carcinogenic. The biogenesis of these halogenated metabolites has not been studied but presumably they all derive, in various ways, from acetoacetate before and after halogenation. The haloforms no doubt arise from the corresponding acetones by an enzymic haloform reaction but the carbon tetrahalides must result from further halogenation of chloroform and bromoform. It is of interest that methyl iodide has

been found in *A. armata* as the halide is a known⁶² constituent of ocean waters and was assumed to be of biological origin. It is considered to be the source of the methyl chloride in the atmosphere (the major halocarbon⁶³), being formed by nucleophilic reaction of methyl iodide with chloride ion, the more volatile product escaping rapidly into the air.⁶⁴

Bonnemaisonia hamifera elaborates a groups of halogenated heptan-2-ones, predominantly (61),⁶⁵

responsible for its sweet odour, while octenones such as (62) occur in *B. asparagoides*⁶⁶ and *Delisea fimbriata*.⁶⁷ The latter also produces numerous lactones of unusual structure, the fimbrolides,⁶⁸ represented here by (63) and (64).

A number of interesting acetylenic compounds have been found in marine organisms, most of which are halogenated. The sponge *Reniera fulva*⁶⁹ produces a series of open chain compounds, two of which contain bromine, renierin-1 (65) and the corresponding alcohol (renierin-2). However the main group are found in

Laurencia spp., the algal source of many halogenated sesquiterpenes. They are also C₁₅ compounds (presumably derived from a C₁₅ fatty acid) usually in the form of an eight-membered cyclic ether carrying an enyne side chain and one or more halogen atoms. Representative examples are laurencin (66),⁷⁰ chondriol (67)⁷¹ and laureatin (68).⁷² In this area X-ray analysis is again invaluable for structure determination because of the difficulty in assigning structures with certainty by other methods. Synthesis is also very difficult but has been recently achieved⁷³ for laurencin. Chondriol was isolated from an alga originally classified as a *Chondria* spp. but this was revised⁷⁴ to *Laurencia* on chemotaxonomic grounds when the structure of

chondriol was finally established. It is obvious that the number of possible C₁₅ structures of this type is enormous and some variations have already come to light. An unidentified *Laurencia* has yielded a nine-membered cyclic ether (69), (established by X-ray analysis⁷⁵) while rhodophytin (70) is a nine-membered cyclic peroxide. Another compound which clearly belongs to this group is the six-membered cyclic ether dactylin-(71).⁷⁶ It was isolated from the sea here

Aplysia dactylomela (together with the *trans*-enyne isomer⁷⁷) but is no doubt of algal origin.

This review has surveyed briefly the main groups of halogenated marine metabolites. There are others like dysidin (72)⁷⁸ and dysidenin (73),⁷⁹ from the

sponge *Dysidea herbacea*, which are unexpected and difficult to classify. The existence of halogenated marine products is no longer remarkable and the fascination now lies in the discovery of novel structures. Undoubtedly there are surprises in store.

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